

Review

The lysine multi-switch: the impact of lysine methylation on transcription factor properties

Byron Baron^{1,2*}

¹Department of Anatomy and Cell Biology, Faculty of Medicine and Surgery, University of Malta, Msida, Malta.

² Department of Biochemistry and Functional Proteomics, Yamaguchi University Graduate School of Medicine, Ube, Japan.

* Corresponding author, E-mail: angenlabs@gmail.com

Abstract

The amino acid lysine can undergo methylation, acylation, sumoylation or ubiquitination, making it an extremely versatile protein residue. Its involvement in the modulation of protein biological functions through de/methylation on histones has been well studied but only recently has the focus shifted towards this post-translational modification in non-histone proteins particularly transcription factors. Lysine methylation has been found to act as a switch which can directly alter function or stability, as well as indirectly alter binding affinity to target DNA motifs and protein partners. Lysine methylation has been best-studied in the tumour suppressor p53, making it the ideal transcription factor to showcase how these different mechanisms act. Other transcription factors that undergo such a post-translational modification include NFkB, STAT3 and TFIID. More recently a new family of 10 lysine methyltransferases has been described and the interaction of one of them with the ubiquitous transcription factor E4TF1-60 opens a whole new field of transcription factor control. Lysine methylation is involved in a number of diseases and has also been shown to play a role in tumorigenesis. Targetting specifically modified over-active transcription factors is a potential form of anti-cancer therapy although it is a very delicate process, which still requires extensive research.

Keywords

Epigenetics, post-translational modifications, lysine methylation, methyltransferases, transcription factors

Highlights

1. Lysine methylation affects protein function, stability, or interaction to DNA or protein
2. The tumour suppressor p53 can be activated and suppressed through lysine methylation
3. The ubiquitous transcription factor E4TF1-60 undergoes lysine methylation by EBM
4. Pathologies including cancers are affected by lysine methylation of non-histone proteins
5. Protein de/methylation can be targetted as a form of treatment

List of acronyms

ETS - E26 Transformation-Specific
PTM – post-translational modification
AdoMet - S-adenosyl-L-methionine
SET - Su(var)3-9, Enhancer of Zeste, Trithorax
SPOUT - SpoU and TrmD
PRMT - arginine(R)-methyltransferases
PKMT - lysine(K)-methyltransferases
LSD1 - Lysine-specific demethylase 1
MDM2 - Mouse double minute 2 homologue
Tip60 - 60 kDa Tat-interactive protein
PUMA - p53 upregulated modulator of apoptosis
Smyd - SET and MYND domain
53BP1 - p53 binding-protein 1
NFkB - Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells

NSD1 - Nuclear Receptor Binding SET Domain Protein 1
IL - interleukin
FBXL11 - F-box and leucine-rich repeat protein 11
TNF- α - tumour necrosis factor alpha
GLP - G9a-like protein
STAT3 - Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3
TFIID - transcription factor IID
TBP - TATA box-binding protein
TAFs - TBP-associated factors
ER α - Oestrogen receptor α
AR - Androgen receptor
RAR α - retinoic acid receptor α
PCAF - P300/CBP-associated factor
E2F1 - E2F Transcription Factor 1
E4TF1 - Adenovirus E4 Transcription Factor 1
ETS - E26 Transformation-Specific
SP1 - Specificity Protein 1
YY1 - Yin Yang 1
NRF-1 - Nuclear respiratory factor 1
OST - On-SighT domain
PCG1 - peroxisome proliferative-activated receptor gamma, coactivator-1
p300/CBP - CREB-binding protein
MAP kinase - Mitogen-activated protein kinases
EBM - E4TF1-binding methyltransferase
METTL - Methyltransferase-Like
FOXK1 - Forkhead Box K1

RPL3 - ribosomal protein L3
 BLAST - Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
 HA - human influenza hemagglutinin
 GFP - Green Fluorescent Protein
 ID - intellectual disability
 VEGFR1 - Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor Receptor 1
 AML1 - Acute Myeloid Leukaemia 1
 SUV39H1 - Suppressor Of Variegation 3-9 Homolog 1
 HSP - Heat Shock Protein
 AURKB - Aurora Kinase B
 INCENP - Inner Centromere Protein
 CPCs - Chromosomal Passenger Complexes

Introduction

Epigenetic changes to proteins are grouped under the general heading of post-translational modifications (PTMs). This covers the addition of a whole range of very different chemical groups which are described as: phosphorylation, methylation, sumoylation, neddylation, acetylation or ubiquitination. Which protein residues can undergo which of the aforementioned modifications ultimately depends on the chemical nature of the individual amino acids. Lysine residues, for example, can undergo all of the above [1], although a specific lysine residue might undergo only one or a few of these.

The presence of PTMs on proteins provides a greater range of flexibility to control and modify protein properties through minimal cellular energy investments, making it faster and more efficient for a cell than having to design and produce a larger number of almost identical proteins to control changes in cellular processes. In tangible terms the property changes observed are linked to: functionality (domain activity), interaction strength (to other proteins, substrates or target DNA), localisation (via translocation) and lifespan (stability).

While in general a specific PTM can cause only one or a few of the above effects, protein methylation has been found to cover the whole range of outcomes depending on the type of protein target, the location of the residue within that protein and the cellular context of such a methyl addition or removal. Most notable, methylation is known for its activity at a DNA level on specific cytosine bases, particularly at CpG islands in gene promoters and enhancers and at a protein level on lysine and arginine residues, prevalently of histone tails [2,94]. However as is now evident, protein methylation is not limited to histones and the role it plays in non-histone proteins is becoming a hot topic because of its multiple modes of protein function modulation.

Protein methylation

There is a wide variety of protein methylation which can be sub-divided into a number of classes. N-methylation predominantly occurs on arginine and lysine but can occasionally be found on histidine, glutamine and asparagine residues [4-6]. O- and S-methylation are known to affect glutamine, asparagine and cysteine residues [7,8]. Methylation of proteins at the N- or C-terminal has

also been observed [9-11]. Unlike acetylation and phosphorylation which present themselves as single modifications, methylation can result in mono-, di- or tri- methylation of specific lysine residues [12] and therefore, both the location and degree of methylation are important for a specific change to protein properties [13,14].

The addition of a methyl group to protein residues is catalysed by methyltransferases, which transfer a methyl group from a donor, which tends to be S-adenosyl-L-methionine (AdoMet), to an acceptor molecule which in addition to proteins can be DNA, RNA, lipids, or even small metabolites [15-17]. There are three superfamilies of methyltransferase enzymes, based on structural similarities. These are the SET (Su(var)3-9, Enhancer of Zeste, Trithorax), the SPOUT (SpoU and TrmD) and the seven- β -strand methyltransferases [16]. The seven- β -strand group includes all arginine(R)-methyltransferases (PRMT) and the SET group contains almost all lysine(K)-methyltransferases (PKMT) [18]. The reverse reaction i.e. the removal of a methyl group from a methylated protein residue is carried out by demethylases such as Lysine-specific demethylase 1 (LSD1) in the case of lysine residues [19].

Lysine methylation of non-histone proteins

Lysine methylation of non-histone proteins, namely di- and tri-methylation of ribosomal proteins, has been known for almost 4 decades [20]. In one of the earliest reports, ten to twenty percent of total 40s and 60s ribosomal sub-units in HeLa cells were found to be methylated at lysine, with trimethylation being most dominant [20]. However, only recently, has lysine methylation of non-histone proteins started to gain momentum and is now becoming an emerging new research focus within PMTs [21].

The biological functions modified by lysine methylation can be divided into two distinct categories: direct and indirect modulation. Direct modulation involves changes to protein function or stability, while indirect modulation involves changes in the interaction affinity to DNA (e.g. gene promoters) or proteins (e.g. co-activators). Having one or more methyl groups on a lysine residue can therefore either block particular interactors from binding or alternatively create new interaction sites for proteins that bind preferentially to the methylated form due to their ability to specifically recognise such a signal. Additionally, the fact that lysine can undergo various PTMs, provides a further level of regulation, since the presence of one PMT inhibits reactions that add alternate modifications. Moreover, methylation can also be interpreted differently by different effector proteins [22], allowing for a single change to give context-specific downstream signalling.

The tumour suppressor p53: exemplifying properties altered by lysine methylation

One of the best non-histone protein which can be used to exemplify how lysine methylation alters protein function, stability and interaction affinity, is the tumour suppressor p53, which is a transcription factor covering important roles

in cell cycle control, apoptosis, and DNA repair following double-strand breaks due to genotoxic stresses [23,24]. This transcription factor is known to undergo methylation, acetylation, ubiquitination or sumoylation at lysine residues K370, K372 and K382 [25-28]. However, while acetylation can only lead to activation of p53 function, methylation can trigger activation or suppression of function depending on the position and degree (i.e. mono-, di or tri-methylation). The properties of p53 controlled by lysine methylation are summarised in Table 1.

Type	Site	Degree	Enzyme	Effect	Reference
Direct:					
Function	K372	Mono-methylation	SET7/9	Transcriptional activation	Ivanov <i>et al.</i> , 2007; Karash <i>et al.</i> , 2008.
Stability	K372	Mono-methylation	SET7/9	Enables subsequent acetylation	Ivanov <i>et al.</i> , 2007.
Indirect:					
DNA affinity	K372	Mono-methylation	SET7/9	Enhances transcription of p21 and PUMA	Chukrov <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Ivanov <i>et al.</i> , 2007.
	K370	Mono-methylation	Smyd2	Suppresses transcription of p21 and mdm2	Huang <i>et al.</i> , 2006.
	K382	Mono-methylation	SET8	Suppresses gene-specific transcription	Shi <i>et al.</i> , 2007.
Protein affinity	K370	Di-methylation	unknown	Increases affinity for the co-activator 53BP1	Huang <i>et al.</i> , 2007; Kachinskai <i>et al.</i> , 2008.
	K370	Demethylation	LSD1	Reduces affinity for the co-activator 53BP1	Nakayama <i>et al.</i> , 2001; Huang <i>et al.</i> , 2007.
	K372	Mono-methylation	SET7/9	Enables interaction with Tip60	Karash <i>et al.</i> , 2008.
	K382	Di-methylation	unknown	Strengthens the interaction with 53BP1	Kachinskai <i>et al.</i> , 2008.

Table 1 Summary of functional changes brought about by lysine demethylation of the transcription factor p53.

Direct modulation of p53 function is taken to be any form of transcription activation. This is observed upon mono-methylation of K372, catalysed by SET7/9, following DNA damage with the consequence of cell cycle arrest or the activation of apoptosis [29,30]. Stabilisation of p53 is controlled also through K372 mono-methylation by SET7/9, affecting the modulation of other PTMs at the C-terminus. It promotes acetylation which increases stability by preventing Mouse double minute 2 homologue (MDM2)-dependent ubiquitination and degradation [23,26,29,30].

Indirect modulation of p53 function through enhanced transcription of target genes (most notably p21 and p53 upregulated modulator of apoptosis (PUMA)) is the result of K372 mono-methylation by SET7/9 in response to DNA lesions, resulting in cell cycle arrest at the G1 phase and inducing apoptosis [23,29,31]. Similarly, suppressed transcription effects are the result of K370 mono-methylation by Smyd2 (SET and MYND domain 2), which decreases p53 binding to the p21 and mdm2 gene promoters, and inversely, a decrease in Smyd2 levels enhances p53-mediated apoptosis. This system has been shown to allow an inactive reserve of p53 to be available for immediate response to DNA damage [25]. Thus modulation of p53 transcriptional activity is based on the interplay between Smyd2-dependent K370 mono-methylation (dissociating p53-DNA complexes) and SET7/9-dependent K372 mono-methylation (increasing p53-

affinity to gene promoters by blocking Smyd2-mediated p53 methylation). Suppression of gene-specific p53-dependent transcription can also be the result of K382 mono-methylation by SET8 [32]. Interestingly, after DNA damage, total p53 and acetylated K382 levels increase while mono-methylated K382 levels decrease. This implies that there is competition between acetylation and methylation [32].

Control of protein interactions involve changes in p53 affinity for the co-activator p53 binding-protein 1 (53BP1), which can be increased by K370 di-methylation, that then binds to the tandem Tudor domain and leads to enrichment of the p21 gene promoter with p53 [33,19]. K370 is demethylated by LSD1, negatively controlling the interaction between p53 and 53BP1 and thus suppressing p53 transcriptional activity [28,19]. Similarly, K382 di-methylation has a high affinity for the Tudor domain of 53BP1 [33] and endogenous di-methylated K382 levels increase after DNA lesions, resulting in strengthening of the interaction between p53 and 53BP1 that provides stabilisation and accumulation of intracellular p53 reserves at the sites of DNA damage, although p53-mediated trans-activation is not affected [33]. In another instance, K372 mono-methylation enables interaction with the chromodomain of acetyltransferase 60 kDa Tat-interactive protein (Tip60), which is responsible for p53 acetylation and is also implicated in controlling its apoptotic function [30].

Lysine methylation controls a wide range of transcription factor properties

Lysine methylation has been shown for p53 to modify various properties. The same can also be said in the case of other non-histone proteins that undergo such PTMs. The number of these proteins is growing fast and includes transcription factors, hormone receptors, signal transducers, chaperones, ribosomal and cytoskeletal proteins [34-37]. However in this section the focus will be on transcription factors.

The most noteworthy transcription factor influenced by lysine methylation is Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NFkB) since this PTM can affect stability, activation and transcriptional activity by modifications at different locations. NFkB is activated by K218 mono-methylation and K221 di-methylation in the relA sub-unit, which are added by Nuclear Receptor Binding SET Domain Protein 1 (NSD1) in response to an activation signal e.g. interleukin (IL)-1 [34] and removed by F-box and leucine-rich repeat protein 11 (FBXL11) (which leads to NFkB inactivation). Interestingly, FBXL11 is induced by NFkB, which produces a negative feedback loop [38]. Proteosomal degradation of promoter-bound NFkB can be initiated by K314 and K315 mono-methylation in relA by SET7/9 in response to NFkB activation e.g. in response to tumour necrosis factor alpha (TNF-α) [39] and this therefore negatively regulates transcription of its target genes, IL-8 and IL-6[39]. Promoter-binding ability (stability of relA-DNA complexes) of relA is modulated through K37

methylation by SET7/9 in the nucleus, thus regulating the recruitment of relA to particular NFκB-regulated gene promoters [40]. In a completely opposite manner, K310 mono-methylation of relA suppresses NFκB target genes through the binding of G9a-like protein (GLP), which can be blocked by S311 phosphorylation, thus driving gene expression [41]. Besides the specificity of function, the location is also essential for such PTMs to occur in the sense that methylation of NFκB occurs only when it is in the nucleus and can bind to DNA [39]. It has been shown that methylation of relA by SETD6 occurs on the chromatin-associated protein [41] and that relA is not associated with histone-modifying enzymes until it is activated [34].

In the case of Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3), lysine methylation affects its DNA-binding potential. K140 di-methylation by SET7/9 in response to IL-6 blocks binding of STAT3 to DNA and this effect can be reversed by LSD1 demethylation [35]. As for NFκB, STAT3 must enter the nucleus and bind to DNA to be methylated. Additionally, phosphorylation induced by IL-6 at S727 (in the transactivation domain), occurs prior to methylation [35].

Lysine methylation appears to also play a key role in the function of the basal eukaryotic transcription factor IID (TFIID) complex, composed of the TATA box-binding protein (TBP) and more than ten TBP-associated factors (TAFs). The TAF7 and TAF10 subunits are mono-methylated by SET7/9 at K5 [42] and K189 [43] respectively, increasing binding affinity for RNA polymerase II and overall transcription activity due to its critical role in proper architecture and stability of the TFIID complex.

Despite the resultant effect of modification might be the same, the mechanisms through which these results are obtained can be very different. Lysine methylation of the two steroid hormone receptors, Oestrogen receptor α (ERα) and Androgen receptor (AR), results in enhancing transcription activity in both cases, however the modes of action are completely unrelated. In the case of ERα mono-methylation at K302 by SET7/9, there is receptor accumulation and stabilisation in the nucleus, which leads to transcription of ERα-target genes [44]. On the other hand K632 methylation by SET7/9 enhances transcription activity by facilitating inter-domain interaction and recruitment to target genes [45]. Interestingly in ERα, K302 mono-methylation can counteract ubiquitination and subsequent degradation of ERα, while mutation of K303 deteriorate methylation of K302, providing evidence for competition between methylation, acetylation and ubiquitination, as well as cross-regulation of neighbouring amino acid modifications [44].

Yet another nuclear receptor, the retinoic acid receptor α (RARα), undergoes activation through lysine modification of two separate properties in response to retinoic acid. RARα is mono-methylated at K109 and K171, and tri-methylated at K347 [46,47]. K109 (located in the DNA-binding domain)

and K171 (located in the receptor loop) mono-methylation are essential for RXR-RAR hetero-dimerisation and trans-activation [47], while K347 (localised in the RARα ligand-binding domain) tri-methylation positively regulates RARα activation by retinoic acid by providing a hydrophobic binding-site for the co-activator P300/CBP-associated factor (PCAF), and enable hetero-dimerisation of the RXR-RAR receptors [46].

Lysine methylation can occur not only in response to a particular ligand but also in response to a particular cellular context such as DNA damage or hypoxia as in the case of E2F Transcription Factor 1 (E2F1) and the chromatin-remodelling factor Reptin. E2F1 is methylated at K185 by SET7/9, thus preventing it from accumulating during DNA damage. On the other hand, once K185 is demethylated by LSD1, E2F1 is stabilised again. Furthermore, K185 methylation has a direct effect on other PTMs since it inhibits acetylation and phosphorylation but stimulates ubiquitination, which causes its degradation [48]. Similarly, Reptin is methylated specifically under hypoxic conditions. K69 methylation by G9a, allows it to bind to the promoters of a sub-set of hypoxia-responsive genes [49].

Adenovirus E4 Transcription Factor 1 (E4TF1-60): a ubiquitous transcription factor altered by lysine methylation

The adenovirus E4 Transcription Factor 1 (E4TF1, also referred to as GABP) is composed of two subunits with predicted molecular weights of 60 and 53kDa respectively [50]. The E4TF1-60 (GABPα) subunit contains a DNA-binding winged-helix-turn-helix domain at the C-terminus, which binds to purine-rich sequences containing a 5'-GGAA/T-3' core motif. These are the typical characteristics of the E26 Transformation-Specific (ETS) protein family [51-60]. The uniqueness of E4TF1-60 as an ETS factor is that it forms obligate heterodi- or tetramers with E4TF1-53 depending on the presence of single or tandem ETS consensus motifs within promoter regions [50,55,56,61-63]. Additionally, single E4TF1-binding sites tend to be adjacent to binding sites for other transcription factors such as Specificity Protein 1 (SP1), Yin Yang 1 (YY1) or Nuclear respiratory factor 1 (NRF-1) [63].

E4TF1-60 can interact with other proteins via three domains: an On-Sight (OST) domain at the N-terminus (which has an overall negative charge and thus useful for binding positively charged partners) [64], a pointed (PNT) domain in the mid-section [65,66] and a domain for binding the ankyrin repeats of E4TF1-53 at the C-terminus, downstream of the DNA-binding domain [52,53].

The E4TF1 complex can thus recruit various co-activators like for example peroxisome proliferative-activated receptor gamma, coactivator-1 (PCG1) and CREB-binding protein (p300/CBP) to promote transcription [67,68]. This ability to bind to other proteins and co-operate with other transcription factors allows it to modulate transcription in specific contexts making it both an effective activator or

histone proteins has also been linked to some diseases [80-82]. However, this section will focus specifically on the role of lysine methylation of non-histone proteins in tumorigenesis using three well-known examples.

Species	Protein Sequence
Homo sapiens	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE
Mus musculus	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE
Gallus gallus	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE
Anolis carolinensis	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE
Xenopus laevis	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE
Danio rerio	RTGNHQ Q Q WQ LLELLTKDKARDCCISW GDESEY K NQPELVACNGQRKHKPTINYE

Figure 2 Alignment of the protein sequences for the DNA-binding domain of E4TF1-60 from 6 vertebrate species encompassing the major taxonomic groups, indicating that K359 has been retained throughout, making it an ideal candidate for functional control through methylation.

The tyrosine kinase Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor Receptor 1 (VEGFR1) is involved in angiogenesis and cancer metastasis. VEGFR1 is a target of Smyd3, which has been shown to be highly expressed in colon, liver and breast carcinomas. The enhanced kinase activity brought about by the dimethylation of the kinase domain (at K831) and increased autophosphorylation induce tumour growth [83].

The transcription factor Acute Myeloid Leukaemia 1 (AML1) gene undergoes chromosomal translocations and point mutations in lymphoid and myeloid leukaemias, leading to the formation of fusion proteins which cause dysregulation in hematopoietic cells. Lysine methylation of the Runt domain in AML1 by Suppressor Of Variegation 3-9 Homolog 1 (SUV39H1) leads to down-regulation of promoter transactivation by reduction of DNA-binding ability as well as changes in nuclear localisation patterns [84].

Heat Shock Protein (HSP) 70 methylation has been known to occur for the past 30 years [85,86] and K561 methylation (as well as C-terminal phosphorylation) of this protein have been found to be associated with increased proliferation rates in cancer cells [87,88]. K561 di-methylation, most probably by SETD1A, regulates the sub-cellular localisation of HSP70 and promotes cellular proliferation in lung, bladder, colorectal and liver cancer cells among others through its interaction with Aurora Kinase B (AURKB) [88]. K561 di-methylation has a critical role in regulating AURKB autophosphorylation (directly influencing kinase activity) and its interaction with Inner Centromere Protein (INCENP), which is essential for the formation of Chromosomal Passenger Complexes (CPCs), and thus cell cycle progression [89,90]. Additionally, HSP90 has been found to be methylated by SMYD2 [91] possibly also playing a similar role in a different biological context.

Possible therapeutic applications

Over-active transcription factors have long been selected for targeting in potential anti-cancer therapy. A small number of transcription factors

seem to be at the core of dysregulation within several human cancers as well as other diseases, making them valid therapy targets to at least control further malignancy and/or metastasis. The advantage of targeting transcription factors is that they are fewer than the effector proteins and well-characterised. However the main disadvantage is that they often play critical roles in more than one transcription activation pathway. Thus it is very difficult to ensure the modulation of transcription factor activity in a controlled manner, particularly if attempting to inhibit the interaction of DNA-binding proteins with their recognition sequences only in specific contexts [92,93]. Although protein de/methylation is known to be linked to disease states, the manipulation through drugs is not straightforward, as one protein covers a wide variety of functions and targets. Ideally the targeting should be specific to only the disease context or with limited side-effects related to the alteration of other important transcription factor or de/methylation enzyme activity.

Conclusion

Lysine methylation has proven to be much more widespread than originally recognised from histone studies. More so since it is now known that there are methyltransferases that do not act on histones such as METTL-family members. The addition of the smallest PTM can exert very significant changes to protein characteristics, both in terms of activity and stability as well as interaction with DNA recognition sites and protein partners. Cross-talk and competition with other PTMs gives an additional level of fine regulation, particularly when it comes to transcription factors and their context-specific activities. Despite the increasing interest in PTMs related to disease, there are few clear examples of how these modifications are directly linked to specific pathologies.

Perspectives

Ongoing research focusing on the lysine methylation of E4TF1-60 is attempting to answer a number of crucial basic questions which include: Does this methylation of E4TF1-60 affect its binding to DNA by directly modifying the DNA-binding domain or through the modified interaction with other proteins? Does EBM target other transcription factors? How many lysine residues on E4TF1-60 can undergo methylation? What degree of methylation do lysine residues in E4TF1-60 undergo? In which biological contexts does this interaction take place? Which biochemical pathways are affected? What are the clinical consequences of this interaction?

Answering these questions will deepen our understanding of the importance of non-histone methylation and its role in ubiquitous transcription. Just as methylation of P53 presented multiple new facets of this protein's function and opened up new possibilities for lysine methylation in general, so will answering the above questions about these two proteins which have been given very limited importance so far, yet present various context-specific transcription scenarios.

References

1. Yang XJ (2005). Multisite protein modification and intramolecular signaling. *Oncogene*, 24(10): 1653-1662.
2. von Holt C (1985). Histones in perspective. *Bioessays*, 3(3): 120-124.
3. Baron B, Sasaki K, Kuramitsu Y, Kitagawa T, Nakamura K, et al. (2012). Isolation and functional analysis of a novel GABPA-interacting co-factor, E4TF-1 Binding Methyltransferase (EBM). *P Malta Med J*.
4. Ishizawa T, Nozaki Y, Ueda T, Takeuchi N (2008). The human mitochondrial translation release factor HMRF1L is methylated in the GGQ motif by the methyltransferase HMPmC. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 373(1): 99-103.
5. Klotz AV, Leary JA, Glazer AN (1986). Post-translational methylation of asparaginyl residues. Identification of beta-71 gamma-N-methylasparagine in allophycocyanin. *J Biol Chem*, 261(34): 15891-15894.
6. Webb KJ, Zurita-Lopez CI, Al-Hadid Q, Laganowsky A, Young BD, et al. (2010). A novel 3-methylhistidine modification of yeast ribosomal protein Rpl3 is dependent upon the YIL110W methyltransferase. *J Biol Chem*, 285(48): 37598-37606.
7. Pegg AE (1990). Mammalian O6-alkylguanine-DNA alkyltransferase: regulation and importance in response to alkylating carcinogenic and therapeutic agents. *Cancer Res*, 50(19): 6119-6129.
8. Sprung R, Chen Y, Zhang K, Cheng D, Zhang T, et al. (2008). Identification and validation of eukaryotic aspartate and glutamate methylation in proteins. *J Proteome Res*, 7(3): 1001-1006.
9. Clarke S (1992). Protein isoprenylation and methylation at carboxyl-terminal cysteine residues. *Annu Rev Biochem*, 61: 355-386.
10. Tooley CE, Petkowski JJ, Muratore-Schroeder TL, Balsbaugh JL, Shabanowitz J, et al. (2010). NRMT is an alpha-N-methyltransferase that methylates RCC1 and retinoblastoma protein. *Nature*, 466(7310): 1125-1128.
11. Wu J, Tolstykh T, Lee J, Boyd K, Stock JB, et al. (2000). Carboxyl methylation of the phosphoprotein phosphatase 2A catalytic subunit promotes its functional association with regulatory subunits in vivo. *EMBO J*, 19(21): 5672-5681.
12. Kouzarides T (2002). Histone methylation in transcriptional control. *Curr Opin Genet Dev*, 12(2): 198-209.
13. Bannister AJ, Schneider R, Kouzarides T (2002). Histone methylation: dynamic or static? *Cell*, 109(7): 801-806.
14. Bannister AJ, Kouzarides T (2005). Reversing histone methylation. *Nature*, 436(7054): 1103-1106.
15. Martin JL, McMillan FM (2002). SAM (dependent) I AM: the S-adenosylmethionine-dependent methyltransferase fold. *Curr Opin Struct Biol*, 12(6): 783-793.
16. Petrossian TC, Clarke SG (2011). Uncovering the human methyltransferase. *Mol Cell Proteomics*, 10(1): M110.
17. Schubert HL, Blumenthal RM, Cheng X (2003). Many paths to methyltransfer: a chronicle of convergence. *Trends Biochem Sci*, 28(6): 329-335.
18. Feng Q, Wang H, Ng HH, Erdjument-Bromage H, Tempst P, et al. (2002). Methylation of H3-lysine 79 is mediated by a new family of HMTases without a SET domain. *Curr Biol*, 12(12): 1052-1058.
19. Huang J, Sengupta R, Espejo AB, Lee MG, Dorsey JA, et al. (2007). p53 is regulated by the lysine demethylase LSD1. *Nature*, 449(7158): 105-108.
20. Chang FN, Navickas IJ, Chang CN, Dancis BM (1976). Methylation of ribosomal proteins in HeLa cells. *Arch Biochem Biophys*, 172(2): 627-633.
21. Huang J, Berger SL (2008). The emerging field of dynamic lysine methylation of non-histone proteins. *Curr Opin Genet Dev*, 18(2): 152-158.
22. Sims RJ rd1, Reinberg D (2006). Histone H3 Lys 4 methylation: caught in a bind? *Genes Dev*, 20(20): 2779-2786.
23. Kruse JP, Gu W (2009). Modes of p53 regulation. *Cell*, 137(4): 609-622.
24. Chumakov PM (2007). Versatile functions of p53 protein in multicellular organisms. *Biochemistry (Mosc)*, 72(13): 1399-1421.
25. Huang J, Perez-Burgos L, Placek BJ, Sengupta R, Richter M, et al. (2006). Repression of p53 activity by Smyd2-mediated methylation. *Nature*, 444(7119): 629-632.
26. Brooks CL, Gu W (2006). p53 ubiquitination: Mdm2 and beyond. *Mol Cell*, 21(3): 307-315.
27. Lachner M, O'Carroll D, Rea S, Mechtler K, Jenuwein T (2001). Methylation of histone H3 lysine 9 creates a binding site for HP1 proteins. *Nature*, 410(6824): 116-120.
28. Nakayama J, Rice JC, Strahl BD, Allis CD, Grewal SI (2001). Role of histone H3 lysine 9 methylation in epigenetic control of heterochromatin assembly. *Science*, 292(5514): 110-113.
29. Ivanov GS, Ivanova T, Kurash J, Ivanov A, Chuikov S, et al. (2007). Methylation-acetylation interplay activates p53 in response to DNA damage. *Mol Cell Biol*, 27(19): 6756-6769.
30. Kurash JK, Lei H, Shen Q, Marston WL, Grandá BW, et al. (2008). Methylation of p53 by Set7/9 mediates p53 acetylation and activity in vivo. *Mol Cell*, 29(3): 392-400.
31. Chuikov S, Kurash JK, Wilson JR, Xiao B, Justin N, et al. (2004). Regulation of p53 activity through lysine methylation. *Nature*, 432(7015): 353-360.
32. Shi X, Kachirskaja I, Yamaguchi H, West LE, Wen H, et al. (2007). Modulation of p53 function by SET8-mediated methylation at lysine 382. *Mol Cell*, 27(4): 636-646.
33. Kachirskaja I, Shi X, Yamaguchi H, Tanoue K, Wen H, et al. (2008). Role for 53BP1 Tudor domain recognition of p53 dimethylated at lysine 382 in DNA damage signaling. *J Biol Chem*, 283(50): 34660-34666.
34. Lu T, Jackson MW, Wang B, Yang M, Chance MR, et al. (2010). Regulation of NF-kappaB by NSD1/FBXL11-dependent reversible lysine methylation of p65. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 107(1): 46-51.
35. Yang J, Huang J, Dasgupta M, Sears N, Miyagi M, et al. (2010). Reversible methylation of promoter-bound STAT3 by histone-modifying enzymes. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 107(50): 21499-21504.
36. Munro S, Khaire N, Inche A, Carr S, La Thangue NB (2010). Lysine methylation regulates the pRb tumour suppressor protein. *Oncogene*, 29(16): 2357-2367.
37. Pless O, Kowenz-Leutz E, Knoblich M, Lausen J, Beyermann M, et al. (2008). G9a-mediated lysine methylation alters the function of CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein-beta. *J Biol Chem*, 283(39): 26357-26363.
38. Lu T, Jackson MW, Singhi AD, Kandel ES, Yang M, et al. (2009). Validation-based insertional mutagenesis identifies lysine demethylase FBXL11 as a negative regulator of NFkappaB. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 106(38): 16339-16344.
39. Yang XD, Huang B, Li M, Lamb A, Kelleher NL, et al. (2009). Negative regulation of NF-kappaB action by Set9-mediated lysine methylation of the RelA subunit. *EMBO J*, 28(8): 1055-1066.
40. Ea CK, Baltimore D (2009). Regulation of NF-kappaB activity through lysine monomethylation of p65. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 106(45): 18972-18977.
41. Levy D, Kuo AJ, Chang Y, Schaefer U, Kitson C, et al. (2011). Lysine methylation of the NF-kappaB subunit RelA by SETD6 couples activity of the histone methyltransferase GLP at chromatin to tonic repression of NF-kappaB signaling. *Nat Immunol*, 2: 29-36.
42. Couture JF, Collazo E, Hauk G, Trievel RC (2006). Structural basis for the methylation site specificity of SET7/9. *Nat Struct Mol Biol*, 13(2): 140-146.
43. Kouskouti A, Scheer E, Staub A, Tora L, Talianidis I (2004). Gene-specific modulation of TAF10 function by SET9-mediated methylation. *Mol Cell*, 14(2): 175-182.
44. Subramanian K, Jia D, Kapoor-Vazirani P, Powell DR, Collins RE, et al. (2008). Regulation of estrogen receptor alpha by the SET7 lysine methyltransferase. *Mol Cell*, 30(3): 336-347.
45. Gaughan L, Stockley J, Wang N, McCracken SR, Treumann A, et al. (2011). Regulation of the androgen receptor by SET9-mediated methylation. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 39(4): 1266-1279.
46. Huq MD, Tsai NP, Khan SA, Wei LN (2007). Lysine trimethylation of retinoic acid receptor-alpha: a novel means to regulate receptor function. *Mol Cell Proteomics*, 6(4): 677-688.
47. Huq MD, Ha SG, Wei LN (2008). Modulation of retinoic acid receptor alpha activity by lysine methylation in the DNA binding domain. *J Proteome Res*, 7(10): 4538-4545.
48. Kontaki H, Talianidis I (2010). Lysine methylation regulates E2F1-induced cell death. *Mol Cell*, 39(1): 152-160.
49. Lee JS, Kim Y, Kim IS, Kim B, Choi HJ, et al. (2010). Negative regulation of hypoxic responses via induced Reptin methylation. *Mol Cell*, 39(1): 71-85.
50. Rosmarin AG, Resendes KK, Yang Z, McMillan JN, Fleming SL (2004). GA-binding protein transcription factor: a review of GABP as an integrator of intracellular signaling and protein-protein interactions. *Blood Cells Mol Dis*, 32(1): 143-154.
51. Watanabe H, Wada T, Handa H (1990). Transcription factor E4TF1 contains two subunits with different functions. *EMBO J*, 9(3): 841-847.
52. Thompson CC, Brown TA, McKnight SL (1991). Convergence of Ets- and notch-related structural motifs in a heteromeric DNA binding complex. *Science*, 253(5021): 762-768.
53. Brown TA, McKnight SL (1992). Specificities of protein-protein and protein-DNA interaction of GABP alpha and two newly defined ets-related proteins. *Genes Dev*, 6(12B): 2502-2512.

54. Flory E, Hoffmeyer A, Smola U, Rapp UR, Bruder JT (1996). Raf-1 kinase targets GA-binding protein in transcriptional regulation of the human immunodeficiency virus type 1 promoter. *J Virol*, 70(4): 2260-2268.
55. Sharrocks AD, Brown AL, Ling Y, Yates PR (1997). The ETS-domain transcription factor family. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol*, 29(12): 1371-1387.
56. Sharrocks AD (2001). The ETS-domain transcription factor family. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*, 2(11): 827-837.
57. LaMarco K, Thompson CC, Byers BP, Walton EM, McKnight SL (1991). Identification of Ets- and notch-related subunits in GA binding protein. *Science*, 253(5021): 789-792.
58. Wasyluk B, Hahn SL, Giovane A (1993). The Ets family of transcription factors. *Eur J Biochem*, 211(1-2): 7-18.
59. Gugneja S, Virbasius JV, Scarpulla RC (1995). Four structurally distinct, non-DNA-binding subunits of human nuclear respiratory factor 2 share a conserved transcriptional activation domain. *Mol Cell Biol*, 15: 102-111.
60. Batchelor AH, Piper DE, de la Brousse FC, McKnight SL, Wolberger C (1998). The structure of GABPalphabeta: an ETS domain-ankyrin repeat heterodimer bound to DNA. *Science*, 279(5353): 1037-1041.
61. Oikawa T, Yamada T (2003). Molecular biology of the Ets family of transcription factors. *Gene*, 303: 11-34.
62. Sawa C, Goto M, Suzuki F, Watanabe H, Sawada J, et al. (1996). Functional domains of transcription factor hGABP beta1/E4TF1-53 required for nuclear localization and transcription activation. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 24(24): 4954-4961.
63. Valouev A, Johnson DS, Sundquist A, Medina C, Anton E, et al. (2008). Genome-wide analysis of transcription factor binding sites based on ChIP-Seq data. *Nat Methods*, 5(9): 829-834.
64. Kang HS, Nelson ML, Mackereth CD, Sch7rpf M, Graves BJ, et al. (2008). Identification and structural characterization of a CBP/p300-binding domain from the ETS family transcription factor GABP alpha. *J Mol Biol*, 377(3): 636-646.
65. Slupsky CM, Gentile LN, Donaldson LW, Mackereth CD, Seidel JJ, et al. (1998). Structure of the Ets-1 pointed domain and mitogen-activated protein kinase phosphorylation site. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 95(21): 12129-12134.
66. Mackereth CD, Sch7rpf M, Gentile LN, MacIntosh SE, Slupsky CM, et al. (2004). Diversity in structure and function of the Ets family PNT domains. *J Mol Biol*, 342(4): 1249-1264.
67. Izumi H, Ohta R, Nagatani G, Ise T, Nakayama Y, et al. (2003). p300/CBP-associated factor (P/CAF) interacts with nuclear respiratory factor-1 to regulate the UDP-N-acetyl-alpha-d-galactosamine: polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase-3 gene. *Biochem J*, 373(Pt 3): 713-722.
68. Wu Z, Puigserver P, Andersson U, Zhang C, Adelmant G, et al. (1999). Mechanisms controlling mitochondrial biogenesis and respiration through the thermogenic coactivator PGC-1. *Cell*, 98(1): 115-124.
69. Genuario RR, Perry RP (1996). The GA-binding protein can serve as both an activator and repressor of ribosomal protein gene transcription. *J Biol Chem*, 271(8): 4388-4395.
70. Rosmarin AG, Caprio DG, Kirsch DG, Handa H, Simkevich CP (1995). GABP and PU.1 compete for binding, yet cooperate to increase CD18 (beta 2 leukocyte integrin) transcription. *J Biol Chem*, 270(40): 23627-23633.
71. Yokomori N, Tawata M, Saito T, Shimura H, Onaya T (1998). Regulation of the rat thyrotropin receptor gene by the methylation-sensitive transcription factor GA-binding protein. *Mol Endocrinol*, 12(8): 1241-1249.
72. Yokomori N, Moore R, Negishi M (1995). Sexually dimorphic DNA demethylation in the promoter of the Slp (sex-limited protein) gene in mouse liver. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 92(5): 1302-1306.
73. Flory E, Hoffmeyer A, Smola U, Rapp UR, Bruder JT (1996). Raf-1 kinase targets GA-binding protein in transcriptional regulation of the human immunodeficiency virus type 1 promoter. *J Virol*, 70:2260-2268.
74. Fromm L, Burden SJ (2001). Neuregulin-1-stimulated phosphorylation of GABP in skeletal muscle cells. *Biochemistry*, 40(17): 5306-5312.
75. Wasyluk B, Hagman J, Gutierrez-Hartmann A (1998). Ets transcription factors: nuclear effectors of the Ras-MAP-kinase signaling pathway. *Trends Biochem Sci*, 23(6): 213-216.
76. Reiff RE, Ali BR, Baron B, Yu TW, Ben-Salem S, et al. (2014). METTL23, a transcriptional partner of GABPA, is essential for human cognition. *Hum Mol Genet*,
77. A Newly Uncovered Group of Distantly Related Lysine Methyltransferases Preferentially Interact with Molecular Chaperones to Regulate Their Activity.
78. Baron B, Kuramitsu Y, Kitagawa T, Nakamura K, Schembri-Wismayer P Comprehensive analysis of downstream targets of the novel protein E4TF1-binding Methyltransferase (EBM) a.k.a. METTL23 (C17orf95). *HUPO 12th Annual World Congress 2013 Abstract Booklet*, 146.
79. Albert M, Helin K (2010). Histone methyltransferases in cancer. *Semin Cell Dev Biol*, 21(2): 209-220.
80. Katz ML, Christianson JS, Norbury NE, Gao CL, Siakotos AN, et al. (1994). Lysine methylation of mitochondrial ATP synthase subunit c stored in tissues of dogs with hereditary ceroid lipofuscinosis. *J Biol Chem*, 269(13): 9906-9911.
81. Chen RL, Siakotos AN, Gao Q, Freiha B, Chin DT (1997). Late-infantile ceroid-lipofuscinosis: lysine methylation of mitochondrial ATP synthase subunit c from lysosomal storage bodies. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1361(1): 66-74.
82. Chen R, Fearnley IM, Palmer DN, Walker JE (2004). Lysine 43 is trimethylated in subunit C from bovine mitochondrial ATP synthase and in storage bodies associated with batten disease. *J Biol Chem*, 279(21): 21883-21887.
83. Kunizaki M, Hamamoto R, Silva FP, Yamaguchi K, Nagayasu T, et al. (2007). The lysine 831 of vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 1 is a novel target of methylation by SMYD3. *Cancer Res*, 67(22): 10759-10765.
84. Chakraborty S, Sinha KK, Senyuk V, Nucifora G (2003). SUV39H1 interacts with AML1 and abrogates AML1 transactivity. AML1 is methylated in vivo. *Oncogene*, 22(34): 5229-5237.
85. Wang C, Lazarides E (1984). Arsenite-induced changes in methylation of the 70,000 dalton heat shock proteins in chicken embryo fibroblasts. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 119(2): 735-743.
86. Wang C, Lin JM, Lazarides E (1992). Methylations of 70,000-Da heat shock proteins in 3T3 cells: alterations by arsenite treatment, by different stages of growth and by virus transformation. *Arch Biochem Biophys*, 297(1): 169-175.
87. Muller P, Ruckova E, Halada P, Coates PJ, Hrstka R, Lane DP, Vojtesek B (2013). C-terminal phosphorylation of Hsp70 and Hsp90 regulates alternate binding to co-chaperones CHIP and HOP to determine cellular protein folding/degradation balances. *Oncogene*, 32:3101-3110.
88. Cho HS, Shimazu T, Toyokawa G, Daigo Y, Maehara Y, et al. (2012). Enhanced HSP70 lysine methylation promotes proliferation of cancer cells through activation of Aurora kinase B. *R Nat Commun*, 3: 1072.
89. Vader G, Medema RH, Lens SM (2006). The chromosomal passenger complex: guiding Aurora-B through mitosis. *J Cell Biol*, 173(6): 833-837.
90. Cooke CA, Heck MM, Earnshaw WC (1987). The inner centromere protein (INCENP) antigens: movement from inner centromere to midbody during mitosis. *J Cell Biol*, 105(5): 2053-2067.
91. Donlin LT, Andresen C, Just S, Rudensky E, Pappas CT (2012). Smyd2 controls cytoplasmic lysine methylation of Hsp90 and myofilament organization. *Genes Dev*, 26: 114-119.
92. Gibbs JB (2000). Mechanism-based target identification and drug discovery in cancer research. *Science*, 287(5460): 1969-1973.
93. Fitzgerald K, Harrington A, Leder P (2000). Ras pathway signals are required for notch-mediated oncogenesis. *Oncogene*, 19(37): 4191-4198.
94. Baron B (2013). Breaking the Silence: The Interplay Between Transcription Factors and DNA Methylation, Methylation - From DNA, RNA and Histones to Diseases and Treatment, Prof. Anica Dricu (Ed.) *InTech*,